

An Empirical Study on Children's Reading Promotion in Rural China: Taking "Holiday Story Club" as an Example

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Abstract: Although there have been some studies on the promotion of reading for rural children in China, they tend to be theoretical and party-political in their stylistic paradigm and textual content. This paper is neither a theoretical output nor a party-political discussion, but a case study based on a real-life scenario of living with children in the countryside. At the same time, the paper also elaborates to varying degrees on what we have seen, heard and thought during this empirical research journey. In addition, the paper also discusses, to varying degrees, the real-life situations faced by rural children in China, and the social and governance problems that have emerged in the field of reading promotion for rural children. It is hoped that this paper can provide an objective reference to the factual scenarios for people in the field, and if it can provide different perspectives for the healthy development of the field of reading promotion for rural children in China in the future, it will also be the research value of this paper.

Keywords: China Public Welfare, Social Development, Chinese Society, Picture Book Reading, Rural Children, Reading Promotion, Children's Education.

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1 Introduction

The author first came into contact with the field of children's reading promotion in 2014, when most areas of China did not have the concept of children's reading promotion, focusing on the field of services related to social welfare organisations are rare, while the same period of time in Europe and the United States is the field of children's reading promotion services have been developed gradually systematic, standardised, so in the knowledge that there is a domestic development of the field to do a part of the strength of the opportunity, the author also immediately began the field of social welfare services. Therefore, after learning that there is an opportunity to contribute to the development of this field in China, the author also began to promote children's reading in the field of social welfare services. The promotion of children's reading is a series of services carried out with "picture books" as the tool carrier. According to Wikipedia, we can find that "Picture book, as its name suggests, is a book of drawings (also translated as a picture book). A picture book is one in which the entire book is based on drawings that can be linked together to form a single complete story. Simply put, as long as the text of the whole book is removed, and the reader can still know what the story of the book is about just by the pictures in the book, then it can be called a picture book. Picture books are often confused with illustration-based storybooks. If the book is text-based, even if there are illustrations on every page, and the text is taken out of the book, if the reader can't

tell the whole story just by looking at the pictures, then it's a storybook. Picture books are divided into age groups, children's picture books are mainly set for young children, children's publications, mostly orientated towards content suitable for young children and children to read, while adult picture books are mainly picture books for adults to read."

After nearly a decade of development since 2014, there are now many social welfare organisations or project partners in China that either focus on children's reading promotion or incorporate children's reading promotion elements into their own projects. This is very gratifying, not only because more and more people are joining or paying attention to the field of children's reading promotion, but also because the author, as an ex-independent children's reading promoter, has experienced a few years of searching for a way to promote children's reading, which convinced her of the importance of promoting children's reading promotion services, and the importance of those who are deeply and effectively involved in the field. The author is convinced of the importance of promoting children's reading services, and the positive impact that excellent children's reading promotion services can bring to children after deep and effective involvement, which is also the unique social value and universal significance of picture books themselves.

Unfortunately, however, in recent years, in the process of the continuous development of China's children's reading promotion services, there have been a lot of potential crises and undesirable phenomena, both explicit and implicit,

especially in the social service paths where commercial development and political orientation are the core elements, and the professional quality of the reading promoters themselves is uneven and their value orientation is too solidified. In addition, with the development of large-scale intelligent technology, the multi-directional diffusion effect that can easily speed up the transmission of social bad habits has also paved the way for the development of such a bad situation in terms of speed of dissemination and coverage. These are not only gradually covering more and more children and teenagers, but also have an unpredictable and irreversible negative effect on the healthy development of children who are still immature. Therefore, the author decided to write this paper to explain to the readers some of the social phenomena that he has found and encountered during his nearly ten years of promoting children's reading in the past.

In terms of the timeline and the commonality of the problematic phenomena, although the content presented in this paper is based on a village children's storytelling session conducted by the author in a rural village in China over a period of nearly 40 days from 17 January 2021 to 25 February 2021, it is worth noting that the presentation of these problems is not limited to this, but rather is a highly universal and similar phenomenon faced by many regions in China. but rather a highly generalised and similar phenomenon that is common to many regions of China.

In terms of the development of geographical levels, in the existing Chinese children's reading promotion services, the best geographical level is the level of big cities, which is far superior to the level of Chinese villages in terms of teachers' strength, financial input, resource supply, social input, hardware and software inclination, and environmental structure. However, as a member of Chinese society and the world community, children have been entrusted with many hopes and trusts since ancient times, be it in the family, the society or the country. Urban children have the advantage of many innate resources that are unattainable for rural children. Although this was not as obvious a decade ago in China's children's reading promotion services, as China's social development process continues to accelerate, the urban population in today's Chinese society has indeed benefited to a relative degree from the popularisation of the concept of children's reading promotion. At the same time, there is a developmental reality that we need to understand: urban children are not representative of rural children, and rural children are not representative of urban children. Although the gap between urban and rural children is gradually narrowing as globalisation continues, the gap between rural and urban children is still very large in the broader context of Chinese society. According to UNICEF public data, by 2015, China's rural children had reached 138 million, accounting for 50.9 per cent of the total child population, with 32.0 per cent of all rural children living in poverty [1].

Whether it is the reading promotion service for urban

children or the reading promotion service for rural children, the author has personally experienced and tried it, in which we can clearly find that rural children are far lower than urban children in terms of acceptance, imagination and future exploration power, etc. Similarly, rural children are far higher than urban children in terms of low self-esteem, panic, restlessness and other negative psychological and mental states. Similarly, in terms of inferiority complex, panic, anxiety and other negative psychological and mental states, rural children are much higher than urban children. Therefore, under the influence of various factors, the author went to a village in China from 17th January 2021 to 25th February 2021 to carry out a public service storytelling activity for rural children, which lasted nearly 40 days.

In addition, from the perspective of national construction and development, children are the future of national development and an important part of the rural population. Promoting the healthy development of rural children's reading is not only an important part of narrowing the gap between urban and rural education levels in the country, but also an important path to promote the realisation of social and educational equity. From Zhou Linxing, Zou Sha, Zhou Li in the "rural children's reading care research in the context of rural revitalisation strategy", we can understand that effective children's reading promotion activities to enhance rural cultural literacy, reserve of human resources, and cultural revitalisation also plays an important role [2]. According to the public information of UNICEF, we can see that by 2015, China's rural children reached 138 million, accounting for 50.9% of the total child population, of which, rural children in poverty-stricken areas accounted for 32.0% of the total number of rural children [1]. This shows that in China's rural areas to carry out children's reading promotion services, so far, still facing an extremely large and complex situation on the severity and importance of the role.

Rural children's reading promotion service is an important part of opening rural children's external horizons. In poor or underdeveloped areas, where the efficient Internet is still not widely available, rural children's acceptance of external information is still mostly confined to the fixed textbook content that is fed to them by their teachers during the stage of China's compulsory education. Nowadays, with the gradual popularisation of short videos, although some rural children have more opportunities to access the outside world through short videos than in the past, similarly, the low quality and fragmentation of the content, the uniformity and rigidity of the model, the stereotypical form and the uniqueness of the consciousness of the short videos themselves, have they really benefited the rural children, who are not mature enough to be able to understand themselves? To a certain extent, it may not only fail to expose rural children to effective and healthy information from the outside world, but also hinder the development of their own creativity, imagination, thinking patterns and mental health. Good and valuable children's reading promotion services, through the gathering and integration of

stories created by many excellent creators from all over the world, coupled with the positive output of a variety of practice modes, can not only help children learn about different stories from all over the world, but also, through the professional and effective organisation and implementation of the activities of the children's reading promoters, can also help children gradually build up a healthier, free, independent and caring attitude. Through the professional and effective organisation and implementation of activities by children's reading promoters, it can also help children gradually build up healthier, free, independent and caring values, which is also the power of the social value of picture books.

This paper is based on the data from the Holiday Storytelling Programme, and aims to present the problems that have arisen in the field of rural children's reading promotion services, and at the end of the paper, the author will present some of the reflections that have been triggered by the programme. At the same time, this article is intended to present readers with a more objective, empirically based picture of the development of reading promotion services for rural children in China, and it is worth noting that the content of this article may conflict with some of the information previously published in China.

2 Literature Review

Chinese society has an important factor that makes it unique from other societies in the world, i.e., the development of Chinese society is based on the Communist Party of China (CPC), which is the only ideological direction and has strong political attributes. Therefore, in the literature research of this paper, considering the unique situation of Chinese society, the author only adopts the literature research in China.

(i) Partial overview of the current state of research in China

After searching in academic data platforms such as China Knowledge Network, Wipo, Wanfang, etc., the authors found that the current status of research available within China is mostly divided into the following segments: research on the regional totality represented by the wide paradigm, e.g., Ma Zhaochen's research on the current situation and development countermeasures based on the western countryside libraries [3]; research on political standpoint represented by party and government, e.g., Zhang Yu and Xiong Jiansheng's research on grass-root level Party organisations to lead the practical exploration of rural cultural revitalisation [4]; research represented by public libraries to help local reading development, for example, Zhang Ping and Sun Zishan and Yue Qianqian and Jia Xinru's research on public libraries' children's reading promotion model for underdeveloped areas - a study on the example of Sichuan Province [5].

(ii) Problems faced in existing studies within China

Taking these three research panels as research references, from which we can see a certain tendency selection behaviour that the current Chinese academia has. From a partial overview of the current state of domestic research, coupled with the direction of output and research content of Chinese academic circles in recent years, we will find that in the current state of China's domestic research, there exists a more centralised, restricted to the influence of the party's ideology of the trend of academic research, which is somewhat deviated from some of the benchmarks for academic research, if we look at the basic norms of academic research from the point of view of truthfulness, objectivity, and validity, many of the existing studies have been found to have a certain tendency to choose their own research. If we look at authenticity, objectivity and validity as the basic norms of academic research, many of the existing research outputs are questionable. During this search for academic resources in the field of reading promotion services for children in rural China, the authors also found that works and people who reduce politicised output and maintain independent academic research content, although relatively rare, still exist, even if politically oriented academic research works seem to blossom as if they were the only ones. In the author's opinion, these conditions may also be one of the reasons why this kind of research content cannot be effectively utilised in practice. This is also the author in the academic data research process, found that some articles, even from the feeling of feeling good, but only choose to give up the citation of the important reasons. Therefore, the research in this paper may rely more on this empirical research process of the discovery and the author of some of the thinking triggered by the process.

(iii) What needs to be added to the existing studies in China

The actual literature cited in this paper is not much, maybe only a few, but it is a very burdensome project in terms of searching, collecting and organising the literature. Admittedly, most of the literature retrieved presents a situation that cannot be adopted due to the lack of objectivity and over-politicisation as mentioned above, but there are still unexpected gains. For example, Bao Chunli and Cao Jianhui, in their article "An Analysis of the Construction of Village Libraries in Gannan Prefecture", mentioned the proposal of raising funds for construction in multiple ways, "Township and village libraries, as a public welfare cultural undertaking, must be supported by government funds, or else it is just a paper exercise. Village library construction should follow the 'government-led, multi-level investment, centralised management, resource sharing, urban and rural integration' investment service system. In view of the local actuality, it can take the way and pipeline of allocating a little bit from the higher government finance, contributing a little bit from the township government finance at this level, financing a little bit from the caring people in the society, and donating a little bit from the energetic enterprises. At the same time, it

is necessary to carry out counterpart support and fixed-point help with state libraries, county libraries, and institutions, and carry out book exchanges and exchanges, so as to guarantee the continuous operation of the library [6]" Then, for example, in the article "Related Thoughts on Construction of Rural Library under the Background of Rural Revitalisation Strategy" by Plateau, the proposal of multilevel linkages for rural libraries is mentioned "The construction of rural libraries, as an important part of rural infrastructure construction, is of great significance to the implementation of the rural revitalisation strategy, and it is also clearly stated in the Rural Revitalisation Strategic Plan (2018-2022) that it is necessary to 'promote the system of county-level libraries and cultural halls as a general branch, give play to the role of radiation of public cultural institutions at the county level, and Strengthen the construction of grassroots comprehensive cultural service centres, achieve full coverage of public cultural services at the rural levels, and enhance service effectiveness', as well as to 'strengthen rural science popularisation work, promote national reading into families and rural areas, and improve the scientific and cultural literacy of farmers [7]' These two materials are in fact also China's domestic These two materials are in fact also frequently mentioned in the content of current academic research, and some of the proposals and ideas given are also very worthwhile to be field-tested, but correspondingly, there are also some problems - different response situations faced by different geographic areas, as well as specific experiments and refinement of the proposed solutions to supplement. These issues are probably what many scholars are thinking about, but since the focus of this paper is on analysing individual cases, the issues are only touched upon.

3 Project Process

3.1 Project Initiation

The Holiday Storytelling Club is based on the social welfare project "Heartfruit Education Reading Companion Programme" initiated by the author in the past, and follows the service concept of the programme, with "To plant the seed of goodness for life" as its mission. The mission of the programme is "To plant the seed of goodness for life", the core of the programme is "To guard the children, to grow with them, to observe life and to explore the world together", and the core of the programme is "To warm each other and to make each other successful. May you be the master of your own destiny and may you have a complete and vivid life" is the slogan of the action. The aim is to help children become full of vitality through the implementation of activities based on life education. The Holiday Storytelling Programme was developed on the basis of this philosophy, and the whole service process was carried out on this basis.

Before the project officially started, the author not only needed to prepare and determine the necessary places,

books, and equipment for the project, but also carried out different degrees of investigation into the local school environment, such as the preliminary research on some rural schools, township schools, and county schools; in the preliminary understanding, the author found that there is a generalised situation of students' excessive pressure in schoolwork and heavy psychological burden among different local schools, In the preliminary research, the authors found that it is common among different local schools that students have too much pressure from schoolwork, too much psychological burden, too little time for extracurricular reading, and not enough knowledge about picture books. This preliminary research not only helped the authors to set up the focus of the project, but also strengthened the authors' determination and confidence to carry out this project.

3.2 Project implementation

1) Examples of the process of project implementation

The official start of the project was on 17th January 2021, which was also the first storytelling session of the Holiday Storytelling Club. A total of seven children came to the first session, and the author narrated the assigned picture book "The Long Night of the Little Mouse" to the children. In the content of the first session, the author drew on the more mature picture book therapy method developed in Japan, and based on this, the author added the content of art therapy. Therefore, after the storytelling of the picture book, the author prepared drawing paper and coloured pencils for the children, and asked them to draw the thoughts they had after the storytelling of the picture book through the form of paintings. In this session, the author only raised the issue of drawing, and did not interfere with the children's choice of what to draw, what colours to use, how to draw, or even whether to draw sitting down or lying down, giving the children what they considered to be a safer space.

The response to the first storytelling session was good. After the first session, some children approached the author to express their feelings about participating in the storytelling session, and some children also expressed their love for the little mouse. Therefore, for the second edition of the storytelling programme, the author chose a series of stories about mice, and the picture book "A Busy Day for a Little Mouse" was the second edition of the storytelling programme, which corresponded to and connected with "A Long Night for a Little Mouse" in the first edition. There were more children in this edition than in the first one, with nine children coming. In this instalment, the author still chose to combine storytelling with a supplementary activity, only this time the choice was no longer painting, but crafting. The author guided the children to make hats by hand. The author also gave the children full freedom to give play to the design, shape, colour and content of the hats, but considering that they might use sharp tools such as stationery knives and scissors, the author not only adopted child-safe scissors and child-safe stationery knives with

protective functions for the selection of tools in the early stage, but also focused on safety hazards at the scene. The site focused on the inspection of safety hazards. In addition, when parents signed up their children for the storytelling activities, the author also informed them in advance of the possible risk factors, risks and other safety aspects, so that they could make the choice of whether to sign up or not, and determine the safety precautions that needed to be done in advance after signing up.

In the fourth storytelling session, the author presented the picture book "Magic Kisses", followed by a drawing session for the children. However, unlike the previous sessions where there was full freedom, the author limited the number and content of the drawings in this session. One drawing was limited to depicting a scene of separation from parents at school, and one drawing was limited to depicting a family relationship in one's heart or in one's imagination. Other than that, the drawing method, colour choice, and drawing posture remained the same as before, without any restriction. At the end of the drawing process, the author had an individual dialogue with each child in a safe environment and asked the children to explain what was depicted in the drawing and what they wanted to say in their hearts. During this individual dialogue, there were children who laughed at the end of the dialogue, and there were also children who shed tears. It is not the author's aim to find out the problem, but the tears of the children are also the author's heartache. For the author, how to help children solve problems is the most important and crucial thing. Therefore, at the end of the session, the author didn't allow the children to take their drawings home as usual, but asked them to leave their own creations behind. After the children had left the site, the author looked at the children's work over and over again, inquiring about and pondering over the signals conveyed in the pictures, which, together with the experience of thinking about the dialogue with the children individually, led to a number of interpretations of the drawings.

Identify problems and solve them. Therefore, after the final interpretation of all the children's picture messages, the author had a full afternoon free to invite some of the children's parents for a dialogue and communication, which fortunately went well for the parents. Unluckily the author's interpretations and the children's messages were real problems that have or are occurring. It should be noted here that the main reason for arranging the drawing of family relationship diagrams for the children is because, on the one hand, it is due to the children's expression of the topic of family in the previous issues of chatting and sharing, on the one hand, it is due to the family relationship featured in the picture book Magic Kissing, and on the other hand, it is due to the author's concern about the children's developmental links, and ultimately the author decided to start a real-world conversation in this form only after reconsideration of a number of factors. It was only after considering a number of factors that the author finally decided to use this format to launch a collision between the real world and the imaginary world. However, what readers and children's reading

promoters need to pay special attention to is that this content can only be carried out when a variety of factors are in place. In addition to requiring the speaker to have a certain degree of professionalism and professional knowledge of psychological healing, it is also very important to the venue, environment, acceptance by children, and the degree of intimacy between the speaker and the target audience. One is not enough. Otherwise, even if it is carried out out of goodwill, if it is carried out easily or inadequately, it is very likely to have reverse problems or even have regrettable or even irreversible consequences.

From the fifth to the thirtieth issue, the author has increased the use of art therapy, psychological healing, logical thinking skills, imagination, creativity, health and wellness, and children's rights, but it is important to point out separately in this that the use of these aspects is not instantaneous, fixed, or used for the sake of using them, but rather, it is a natural choice based on the actual changes that occur at the site of the children, at different time periods, and at different developmental natural choices extended by actual changes in their stages of development. Since this paper is written to show the problems that have arisen in the field of reading promotion services for rural children, and not in terms of the refinement of the content and methods used in the projects and activities, the authors will only make a brief general statement here.

With the passage of time and the increase of activity density, the relationship between the author and the local children has become more and more intimate, in addition to the children looking for the author for chatting and reading, the children's performance in the storytelling sessions has gradually become more and more mischievous accordingly. Therefore, the author after part of the factors of the comprehensive consideration, and then carried out the activities of the points for small gifts, each period of the selection of the highest score of the children in the new period to be rewarded, for the points of the lower score of the children, due to the loss of statistics, the author is unable to present specific evidence to prove that, but there is a point worth noting is that in the records of the existing information, the author has been a successive low score and the scene of some of the problems of the children have been briefly carried out. children with some of the problems in the field.

2) Selection of the number of participants for the programme

In terms of the stricter reference to the ratio of instructors to audience, it would be inappropriate to have more people than the limit of quality protection, but in terms of the author's purpose in organising this event, it is not the boutique classes that are needed, but the universality of the number of participants. In this regard, the authors' current view is that the lack of opportunities for rural children to participate in such a programme is so important that a numerical limit of quality classes for urban children would not be appropriate for the authors' target audience and would

not be in line with the authors' original intention for the programme. Therefore, in terms of the number of participants, all children are welcome as long as the venue can accommodate them. According to the author's statistical data, in this activity, based on 30 storytelling sessions, the actual number of participants was 218, with the highest number of participants in a single session being 13, the lowest number of participants in a single session being 3, and the average number of participants in a single session being 7.26, with the median number of participants in a whole session being 7.

3) Selection of books for project implementation

The selection of illustrated books is never a simple matter, there is no list of books that are necessarily suitable, nor are there books that are not necessarily suitable. And for individual children's bibliographic selection, the degree of difficulty of bibliographic selection is far less than the collective selection, therefore, taking into account the volatility of the project implementation and the children's immediate needs, the author in the final bibliographic selection of the preparation of the order of 100 picture books, although the number of the actual number of books used only 40 books, but for the smooth implementation of the activities is to a certain extent to play the role of a certain degree of protection. The author's final choice of books was to order 100 picture books.

3.3 Project Summary

In terms of the age of the participating children, it covers kindergarten to junior high school; in terms of the source schools of the participating children, it covers rural primary schools, township secondary schools, county primary schools, county secondary schools, and primary schools of municipalities; in terms of the selection of topics of the picture books, it covers the aspects of parent-child relationship, interpersonal communication, personal growth, health, and literary literacy; in terms of the gender of the children participating in the project, the number of times of participation is 153 for girls and 65 for boys; in terms of the improvement of children's abilities, it covers logical thinking, imagination, creativity, self-confidence, oral expression, articulation, mental clarity, and psychological development. In terms of children's participation by gender, in terms of the number of participations, the number of girls' participation was 153, and the number of boys' participation was 65; in terms of children's ability enhancement, it covered logical thinking, imagination, creativity, self-confidence, oral expression ability, clarity of articulation, mental receptivity, and acceptance of novelty, and so on.

Among them, in the aspect of children's ability enhancement, the author's feeling is more profound and specific. After nearly 40 days of the programme, several of the participating children showed a marked improvement in articulation, oral expression and self-confidence compared to the children before the programme. This not only surprised the parents of the children involved, but also gave

the author a sense of the correctness of the programme and, most importantly, the practical benefits that the children gained from the experience.

However, unfortunately, in a follow-up record six months later, although some children were very happy and even excited when they saw the author, after another face-to-face communication and understanding, the author found that one of the two children who had gained a significant improvement in their self-confidence had undergone a major change, from timidity and anxiety when they first participated in the programme in January to confidence at the end of the programme in February, and then to the interview in August half a year later, when the parents of the participating children were surprised. The author was very shocked to find that one of the children's self-confidence had changed dramatically, from timidity at the beginning of the programme in January, to confidence at the end of the programme in February, and then to timidity in the interview in August six months later. After another in-depth conversation, the author also discovered the recurrence of the problem of violence in schools, to which he had not paid enough attention before. The other child, who had previously focused on poor concentration and articulation, was strongly affected by the decline in concentration and articulation in the follow-up interview, although the author was sure that the child had made significant improvements at the end of the programme in February. Perhaps the only joyful thing was that the child's activity level did not decrease, but rather increased. The author remembers that at the end of the interview, the child happily volunteered to dance a piece of a dance that she had just learnt at a dance training class, which the author was very encouraged, honoured and sorry to hear about.

4 Case Study

In the children's reading promotion service, the authors believe that in addition to the professionalism of the reading promoters themselves and their extensive and effective learning, external factors such as the construction of the venue environment, the selection of the book list, the design of the activity form, the enrichment of the activity content, the guarantee of the activity quality, and the change of the stereotyped model are also equally important in order to achieve a real relationship with the service recipients. In addition to the internal factors such as the construction of the venue environment, the selection of book lists, the design of activity forms, the enrichment of activity contents, the guarantee of activity quality, the absence of political awareness, and the change of stereotyped patterns, it is also equally important, and what is more crucial in this regard is that we should really be with the service users, not just dressing up in a formal way, but connecting with them from heart to heart.

Although the "Holiday Storytelling Club" carried out by the author as an individual has achieved good results to a certain extent, it is a gap and lack of reading promotion

services for children in rural areas of China as a whole. Similarly, the author firmly believes that if this project can be used as a constructive reference for colleagues in the field, then the effects of individual cases may turn into gains in overall implementation.

Although this is still difficult in the current Chinese society, it is also important and crucial. At the same time, in addition to form and content, the financial factor is also very important, and can be fatal for many children's reading promotion service providers. It is still very difficult in the current Chinese society not to be subjected to external financial pressure and not to worry about the sudden cut-off of project funds. In this project, the author's funding was based on personal input, not on outside sources, which is extremely difficult for larger and more established children's reading promotion services. The fact that the author was the only person involved in the project, and was not subject to the constraints of funding, organisation or political scrutiny, is probably one of the factors that enabled the author to actually carry out the project.

In the field of children's reading promotion services in China, in addition to the financial pressures faced by service providers, what is even more fraught with uncertainty is the pressurised scrutiny from the variable political factors that are imposed on service providers. Although many scholars talk about keeping government power in a cage, the reality is that the power of many local governments is not only not locked in a cage, but the management authority has become more and more broad, and if you are not careful, you may have to face the situation of being reported, intimidated, and disciplined for political suppression. With such unstable political changes, how can the relevant service providers devote themselves to the study and development of the project and the organisation?

In addition, there is another point that we need to pay attention to, which is the pressure of survival faced by individual staff members. Many children's reading promoters at the grassroots level are mostly relying on their passion to persevere, and it seems to have become an industry practice that they are underpaid and underpaid. A very realistic and teasing scenario is that many outstanding children's reading promoters may not even be able to support themselves. Under such circumstances, relying on spiritual pursuits and ideal ambitions to support the development of the children's reading promotion field in rural China is very difficult and unstable. In addition, for some of the "big bosses" who hold social resources, they may not only fail to give the project staff the economic and resource support they need, but also increase the supply of inputs for "face-saving projects" to save face, and compress the supply of inputs for social welfare organisations who actually do the work. On the contrary, the supply of inputs for "face-saving projects" is being increased step by step, while the supply of inputs for actual social welfare parties is being reduced. Under such circumstances, children's reading promoters at the grassroots level, even if they have high

professional ideals and lofty social ethics, will not be able to continue to support their work. Whether from the individual. Whether individually or as a whole, these are not only the actual conditions prevailing in the field, but also the overall development of Chinese society, which is extremely representative of Chinese society.

The children mentioned by the authors in the above examples of project implementation, especially in the area of capacity enhancement, may seem to be individuals or a small number of individuals, but from the perspective of the development of Chinese society as a whole, they have a considerable degree of universality, as can be seen from the incidents of violence in schools that have continued to be reported on the Internet in the past few years. At the same time, the problem of violence in schools has been occurring continuously in kindergartens, primary schools, junior high schools, high schools, and even universities, to varying degrees. Although the relevant government departments have been intervening, the actual problem has not been effectively solved. In the author's opinion, the ineffective intervention of some government departments has not only failed to solve the problem of school violence, but also exacerbated it to a certain extent. In the beginning, it was an individual incident, but why did the individual incident extend step by step to become a holistic situation? Although these are not within the scope of the author's study, they are also what the author has found and thought about through the implementation of this project, therefore, the author hereby gives a brief overview of the explanation. At the same time, we need to pay attention to the connection between individuality and wholeness in Chinese society. Through this paper, we can learn that the two are not only closely related, but also, to some extent, complementary.

Through the children who suffered from school violence brought up in the "Holiday Storytelling Club", the authors derive the overall situation of school violence in Chinese society, and from this, the development and empirical research of the "Holiday Storytelling Club", though an individual case, is a good example of the relationship between the individual and the whole. Through the reverse verification of school violence, we can find a close connection between individual cases and the overall development of the social landscape. In terms of their apparent starting point, both have gradually developed from an individual to a whole; in terms of the development process, both have the same development path and ineffective mode of dealing with the actual situation of the society and the government; and in terms of the growing environment or the breeding ground, both have the same growing environment, and both have grown up in the authoritarianism of a highly centralised part of the government. At the same time, both are also subject to the inaction, arbitrary interference, and ineffective solutions of partial governments, especially in terms of the misplaced behaviour of partial governments in addressing the actual problems instead of those who raise them.

The uncontrolled power of some governments and the masters of social resources are simultaneously squeezing the healthy development of reading promotion services for children in rural areas in China. From the perspective of the power system of Chinese discourse and the actual landscape of Chinese society, we cannot consider an individual case as a case only; whether from the perspective of the population base or from the perspective of socio-political attributes, the cases that have arisen in many parts of Chinese society have a certain breadth and universality. Whether in terms of population or socio-political attributes, many of the cases in Chinese society are broad and universal in some sense. As part of China's overall promotion of children's reading, in terms of the number of children, according to the data mentioned above, the number of children in the countryside accounts for more than 50 per cent of the total number of children, and with limited resources and policies, and uneven social input, the resources for promoting children's reading for children in the countryside are far less than those available to children in the cities. Children in rural areas receive far fewer resources for promoting children's reading than children in urban areas. Urban children have an inherent resource advantage, which, after political legitimisation, has increased the supply of social resources to a certain extent compared with rural children through a combination of innate resource advantage and acquired policy support. Rural children not only do not have any advantage in terms of innate resources, but the gap between them and rural children is gradually widened through the strategy of unbalanced input supply. Under such a social situation, how can rural children compete, co-operate and grow together with urban children in their future social development? This is the universal social situation that Chinese society is facing, the actual social situation that is occurring in Chinese society, and the problematic situation that the author is worried about in the future of Chinese society - the abnormal widening of the social gap and the urban-rural rift.

5 Conclusion

What kind of problems we are facing and what kind of problems we need to solve. Although the core of this paper has been elaborating on the development of reading promotion services for children in rural areas of China, the problems we are facing, the problems we need to solve, and the corresponding ways and means have also been mentioned throughout this paper. Finding answers from problems, looking at problems from answers. Instead of curing the screening and piecing together a paper author can not avoid must put forward countermeasures, rather put ourselves in the position of re-entering the overall context of the article to find individual or collective want to answer. There is no one suitable solution to the world's problems, especially for Chinese society, which has an even wider scope of relevance. Therefore, for the author, the so-called solution is in fact our own most direct feelings and actions towards these children and this environment.

Finally, I would like to end this article with a paragraph from a former writer, hoping to share the same encouragement with all of you: "Although we often talk about humanities and social sciences, in fact, humanities and social sciences may not be enough to be called a discipline in the true sense of the word, this point is in fact just like the field of engineering, the humanities is humanities, social sciences are social sciences, and each of them has its own unique academic social research significance. They each have their own unique academic social research significance. Although we have different divisions of labour, different duties and different research directions, the social responsibilities that we should undertake are exceptionally the same. No one is better than anyone else, and no one is superior to anyone else. The only thing that we have, and which is also common to all of us, is in fact the most fundamental academic ethics of defying power and living and dying for the people. Do your duty, take responsibility, link academic strength, and jointly promote the healthy development of society, these are not only the mission of academics, but also as a person's life."

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